

Novel Method to compute the Sum of Geometric Series on Real Numbers

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Abstract: Nowadays, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical equations to solve today's scientific problems and meet challenges. In this paper, the author introduces a novel technique to compute the sum of geometric series on real numbers. This computational technique can enable the students and scholars to enhance their research knowledge in the area of computing and mathematical sciences.

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1. Introduction

Geometric series [1-10] played a vital role in differential and integral calculus at the earlier stage of development and still continues as an important part of the study in science, engineering, and management. In this article, the author introduces the sum of geometric series on real numbers in a new way.

2. Computation of Geometric Series

Let x be a variable and it is assumed to a real number. Then, the sums of geometric series are computer on the real number in a novel way.

$$x = x \Rightarrow x = (x - 1) + 1 \Rightarrow x = \frac{x - 1}{x^0} + \frac{x - 1}{x} + \frac{1}{x} \Rightarrow x = \frac{x - 1}{x^0} + \frac{x - 1}{x} + \frac{x - 1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^2}.$$

We can further expand the above expression as follows:

$$x = x \Rightarrow x = \frac{x - 1}{x^0} + \frac{x - 1}{x} + \frac{x - 1}{x^2} + \frac{x - 1}{x^3} + \frac{x - 1}{x^4} + \dots + \frac{x - 1}{x^{n-2}} + \frac{x - 1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{x - 1}{x^n} + \frac{1}{x^n}.$$

$$x = x \Rightarrow \frac{x - 1}{x^0} + \frac{x - 1}{x} + \frac{x - 1}{x^2} + \frac{x - 1}{x^3} + \dots + \frac{x - 1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{x - 1}{x^n} = x + \frac{1}{x^n} = \frac{n^{n+1} - 1}{x^n}.$$

$$x = x \Rightarrow \frac{1}{x^0} + \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^3} + \frac{1}{x^4} + \frac{1}{x^5} + \frac{1}{x^6} + \dots + \frac{x}{x^{n-2}} + \frac{1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{1}{x^n} = \frac{n^{n+1} - 1}{x^n (x - 1)}.$$

$$\text{Therefore, } x = x \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{n^{n+1} - 1}{x^n (x - 1)}.$$

Similarly, we can compute the sums of geometric series for others.

$$1 = 1 \Rightarrow 1 = \frac{x - 1}{x} + \frac{1}{x} \Rightarrow 1 = \frac{x - 1}{x} + \frac{x - 1}{x^2} + \frac{x - 1}{x^3} + \frac{x - 1}{x^4} + \dots + \frac{x - 1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{x - 1}{x^n} + \frac{1}{x^n}$$
$$\Rightarrow \frac{x - 1}{x} + \frac{x - 1}{x^2} + \frac{x - 1}{x^3} + \frac{x - 1}{x^4} + \frac{x - 1}{x^5} + \dots + \frac{x - 1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{x - 1}{x^n} = 1 - \frac{1}{x^n} = \frac{x^n - 1}{x^n}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^3} + \frac{1}{x^4} + \frac{1}{x^5} + \dots + \frac{1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{1}{x^n} = \frac{x^n - 1}{x^n(x-1)} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{x^n - 1}{x^n(x-1)}.$$

$$\therefore 1 = 1 \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{x^n - 1}{x^n(x-1)}.$$

$$\frac{1}{x} = \frac{1}{x} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{x} = \frac{x-1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^2} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{x} = \frac{x-1}{x^2} + \frac{x-1}{x^3} + \frac{x-1}{x^4} + \frac{x-1}{x^5} + \dots + \frac{x-1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{x-1}{x^n} + \frac{1}{x^n}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{x-1}{x^2} + \frac{x-1}{x^3} + \frac{x-1}{x^4} + \frac{x-1}{x^5} + \dots + \frac{x-1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{x-1}{x^n} = \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x^n} = \frac{x^{n-1} - 1}{x^n}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^3} + \frac{1}{x^4} + \frac{1}{x^5} + \dots + \frac{1}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{1}{x^n} = \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x^n} = \frac{x^{n-1} - 1}{x^n(x-1)}.$$

$$\therefore \frac{1}{x} = \frac{1}{x} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=2}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{x^{n-1} - 1}{x^n(x-1)}.$$

$$\text{Also, } \frac{1}{x^2} = \frac{1}{x^2} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=3}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{x^{n-2} - 1}{x^n(x-1)}; \frac{1}{x^3} = \frac{1}{x^3} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=4}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{x^{n-3} - 1}{x^n(x-1)}; \dots;$$

$$\frac{1}{x^{n-1}} = \frac{(x-1)}{x^n} + \frac{1}{x^n} \Rightarrow \frac{(x-1)}{x^n} = \frac{1}{x^{n-1}} - \frac{1}{x^n} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=n}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{x-1}{x^n(x-1)}; \text{ and } 0 = \frac{1-1}{x^n(x-1)}.$$

Theorem 2.1: $\sum_{i=0}^n (i+1) \times \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{n^{n+1} - n}{x^{n-1}(x-1)^2}, x \neq 1.$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=2}^n \frac{1}{x^i} + \dots + \sum_{i=n}^n \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{x^{n+1} - 1}{x^n(x-1)} + \frac{x^n - 1}{x^n(x-1)} + \dots + \frac{x-1}{x^n(x-1)} + \frac{1-1}{x^n(x-1)}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1) \times \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{1}{x^n(x-1)} \{(1+x+x^2+x^3+\dots+x^{n-1}+x^n+x^{n+1}) - (n+1)\}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1) \times \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{1}{x^n(x-1)} \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^n x^i - (n+1) \right\}, \text{ where } \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} x^i = \frac{n^{n+2} - 1}{x-1}.$$

$$\text{Then, } \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1) \times \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{1}{x^n(x-1)} \left\{ \frac{n^{n+2} - 1}{x-1} - (n+1) \right\} = \frac{1}{x^n(x-1)} \left\{ \frac{n^{n+2} - 1 - nx + 1}{x-1} \right\}.$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1) \times \frac{1}{x^i} = \frac{n^{n+1} - n}{x^{n-1}(x-1)^2}, x \neq 1.$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, the author has introduced the sums of geometric series on real numbers in a novel way. This idea can enable the researchers to be involved in the scientific research on computing and mathematical sciences.

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